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ISSN (2790-976X)

Research on the Connotation-Narrowing of Labor Education and Its Reasons in China's Elementary Education in the New Era

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Received Date: 14-July-2022 Accepted Date: 24-Aug-2022 Published Date: 30-Sep-2022

Abstract: *The policy document “the Opinions on Comprehensively Strengthening Labor Education in Colleges and Primary Schools in the New Era” pointed out the direction for the development of labor education in the new era. The natural ecological connection between the vast rural world and labor education makes the countryside the natural field for the implementation of labor education. However, in many rural schools, labor education has been misinterpreted, resulting in the narrowing and alienation of labor education. Labor education is regarded as “the teaching of labor knowledge” and is replaced with “intellectual education”, the reasons of which mainly lie in: firstly, rural families’ traditional concept on laboring and their prejudice on the labor education. Secondly, the rural school education’s lack of teachers, and the rural teachers’ limited knowledge level as well as their partial understanding of the connotation of labor education. Moreover, the negative influence of the connotation-narrowing on labor education is that it separates man and nature, the body and heart, as well as students’ knowing and doing, which means it replaces vivid “laboring activities” with passive “classroom-teaching”, vast rural fields with narrow classrooms, and students’ “physical and mental development” with teachers’ “one-man show”.*

Keywords : *labor education; rural school; connotation-narrowing*

1. Introduction

In recent years, strengthening labor education has become the consensus of the government, the country and the whole society, which provides fundamental principles for comprehensively strengthening labor education in the new era. [1] On March 20, 2020, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council promulgated officially the *Opinions on Comprehensively Strengthening Labor Education in Colleges and Primary Schools in the New Era*, which pointed out the direction for the development of labor education in primary and secondary schools in the new era. Therefore, labor education has attracted much attention and become a hot topic in the current education reform [2]. Labor education is a necessary component of all-round development education, which has a unique educational value and

determines directly the laboring spirit outlook, laboring value orientation and laboring skill level of the socialist builders and successors. However, at present, the unique educational value of labor has been ignored to some extent, and labor education has been weakened and marginalized, so that "some students' labor concept is weak, labor habits are defective, and labor ability is degraded". [3]

The countryside of China is based on labor, and labor is the source of almost all wealth. There is a natural ecological connection between the vast rural world and labor education, making countryside the natural field for the implementation of labor education. Rural school education should have promoted the rural education reform through the strong call for labor education in the new era, forming its own characteristics of education reform, and narrowing the gap with urban education. However, by reasons of that the rural school education is relatively backward and its teachers are weak compared with those of urban school, there have been some problems in labor education of rural school in recent years, which mainly contains the negative effect of the rural people's one-sided concept about labor, the suppressing effect produced by the exam-oriented education ecology in rural school and so on. As a result, the development of labor education in rural schools is beset with difficulties. [4] Labor education has been misinterpreted in rural school education, which has resulted in the narrowing and alienation of labor education in rural schools. Under the background of the "Strategy For Rural Revitalization" and when labor education is restored to the national education system, it is of certain practical significance to discuss the related problems of labor education in rural schools.

2. To avoid the connotation-narrowing, labor education should be carried out through Laboring

The connotation-narrowing of labor education in rural schools means: due to the pressure and influence from such factors as parents (some parents have the traditional idea of "All things are inferior, but learning is superior"), the influence of exam-oriented education and its enrollment rate, or some rural teachers' partial understanding on labor education, then labor education in rural schools is always regarded as "the teaching of labor knowledge", and is replaced with "intellectual education", and they implement labor education simply through teachers' teaching in the classroom and explaining the knowledge about laboring. However, the fact and truth is that realizing the goal of labor education depends fundamentally on labor practice. This is because labor practice, as a basic form of social practice, is a physical or manual concept (people's bodies "participate" in activities, involving using the hands or physical strength), putting it in another way: laboring practice is physical, situational, generative and integrated [5].

The physical or manual concept of labor determines that labor practice is the unity of laborers' transformation of the external world and their own subjective world, and determines that its educational value is holographic. That is, through laboring practice, students can overcome the wrong idea that they despise manual labor and manual workers. Thus, students can develop the laboring quality to create a better life, they know there is no difference between the so-called noble labor and low labor. Moreover, labor education can help students develop their qualities of industry, thrift, frugality, struggle, innovation, dedication and other fine qualities, and labor education enables students to engage both in non-productive and productive labor to achieve relevant basic knowledge and skills, to "consolidate, expand and deepen their cultural and scientific knowledge learned in the classroom, and help teachers improve their teaching effect". [6]

3. The reason of the connotation-narrowing on labor education

Rural schools' labor education has been narrowed for many reasons, mainly in the following two aspects. First of all, most rural families have been living on agriculture for generations, and they think they have been suffering enough from the "pain of farming". Moreover, in rural society, these traditional concepts prevail, such as "those who labor with minds govern others, those who labor with physical strength are governed by others", "all things are inferior, only learning is superior (learning is above doing any other things; learning is the noblest of human pursuits)" and so on, which reinforces the prejudice of rural parents against labor. Their deep aspiration of "leaving the farm to the city" influences children's cognition of labor and labor education imperceptibly, and often turns into pressure on rural school teachers, resulting in the obstruction of the implementation of labor education.

Second, the rural school education has always been the weakest link in our education system. Such reasons as lack of teachers, teachers' limited knowledge level, some rural teachers' partial understanding of the connotation of labor education in the new era, the weakness of their labor education consciousness etc., lead to the fact that the educational function of labor education is neglected in rural school education. In addition, affected by exam-oriented education for a long time, rural school teachers' education focus almost on the enrollment rate, and some teachers are eager to get quick success and instant benefits, which makes them narrow the connotation of labor education and choose to resort to the traditional "classes", such as the history lesson on the history of human's laboring, a Chinese lesson on the working people, a geography lesson on agricultural geography. The factors above hinder and restrict the implementation of labor education in rural schools, and finally narrow it into the "traditional education of teaching laboring knowledge".

4. The negative influence of the connotation-narrowing on labor education

It should be pointed out that such connotation-narrowing is to a great degree the negation of the strong function of labor education in rural schools. On the one hand, it denies the fundamental purpose of labor education. The labor education of socialism contains the problem of "the purpose of education: cultivating talents for whom" – and its answer is to cultivate talents for the happiness of majority of working people. Therefore, labor education must firstly be "the education for the people who laboring for a life (including every students)", that is to say it is a kind of people-oriented education. The education of "teaching laboring knowledge in classroom" is, however, the traditional educational paradigm of the Herbart era, which centers on the teacher, the textbook, the class, but in these "centers," the student is not "present." It is only a one-way and cold process of knowledge-transferring, because students have no experience, and if there is no experience, how can they develop and transform their experience? Though, the education of "teaching laboring knowledge in classroom" can enable students to understand, learn and memorize laboring knowledge systematically, but no matter how lively the classroom is, no matter how the teacher designs it, and no matter how the teacher and student interact with each other, it can never make up for its innate deficiency, because it is not the source of knowledge, and students cannot connect it with the real life.

On the other hand, this kind of narrowing negates the connotation and essence of labor education -- "labor education should be carried out through laboring". Labor education is the unity of labor and education, which regards the human nature as a component, so that people can interact with the vast space environment and seek to adapt to the environment, through participating in labor activities and this kind of process develop students both physically and mentally. However, the education of "teaching laboring knowledge in

classroom" is not the education "in the laboring activities", which separates man and nature, separates the body and heart, separates knowing and doing. This kind of education is carried out in the narrow and passive "classroom teaching" instead of the spacious and vivid "field", in the teachers' "monologue" instead of "linkage" of students' body and mind. That is to say, the connotation-narrowing on labor education replaces vivid "laboring activities" with passive "classroom-learning", vast rural fields with narrow classrooms, and students' physical and mental development with teachers' "one-man show". Totally speaking, the narrowing of labor education in rural schools makes the implementation of labor education lose its carrier and become an empty form of "education without labor". The connotation-narrowing from education "in the laboring activities" to the "teaching of laboring knowledge in classroom" is actually not educational. As Dewey said, taking a saw out of the toolbox is not manufacturing a tool [7]. Teachers' "teaching laboring knowledge" on the platform cannot make students gain the true knowledge of the world. Only through the education in laboring itself can students feel and understand labor, construct the meaning of life, cultivate their consciousness, and acquire useful skills and true knowledge.

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